

LEVERAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR ENHANCED E-COMMERCE PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: *Notable advancements in the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in recent years facilitated the integration of AI technologies into e-commerce. This paper emphasizes the practical application of AI in the domain of e-commerce. It will describe how its implementation would lead to improved overall functioning of e-commerce businesses. The focus will be on e-commerce stores utilizing some of the most well-known existing frameworks. The goal is to demonstrate how artificial intelligence technology may have highly positive effects on the functioning of these systems and how it can save business owners additional time or money.*

Keywords: *E-commerce, Artificial Intelligence, Efficiency.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence impacts nearly every sector. As time passes, people are increasingly adopting technologies that are powered and driven by artificial intelligence (Mohammad, 2020). It is increasingly integrated into educational systems, workplaces, and others. It is pervasive, from the self-checkout counters at grocery stores to the advanced security systems in large shopping malls and airports. Thus, even the field of e-commerce business has not remained unaffected.

Electronic Commerce (EC) implies the utilization of the Internet and modern communication technologies for managing business operations and exchanging information. At its core, e-commerce is founded on business models that leverage electronic devices and network technologies. This involves the digitalization of all business processes, covering not only the outward-facing activities such as online marketing, electronic payments, and logistics, but also the internal processes within companies, including Supply Chain Management (SCM), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), Management Information Systems (MIS), Customer Relationship Management (CRM), and Human Resource Management (HRM) (Song et al., 2019). “E-commerce is an economic and technological revolution, it is the product of economic, scientific, technological and cultural development.” (Song et al., 2019).

The development of E-commerce has come a long way from its early beginnings in the late 1970s to the present day. Research on AI in e-commerce has been going on for the past three decades. About 4000 academic research articles have been published on the topic across multiple disciplines, including computer science, marketing, economics, and management, addressing both consumer and organisational aspects (Bawack et al., 2022).

In the past half-decade, e-commerce has experienced explosive growth, transforming the way consumers shop and businesses operate. Studies show that the number of e-commerce transactions increased by an astonishing 77% during the COVID-19 pandemic (Koetsier, 2020). This was also a clear signal that people are ready to embrace online shopping, indicating that investing in developing technology, enhancing e-commerce services, and improving customer experience is worthwhile to sustain the generated interest.

We have reached a stage where entire business models are built on the foundations of e-commerce, thus making even the most minor increases in the efficiency of online stores highly significant for business systems. In this context, artificial intelligence has emerged as a powerful tool that can significantly enhance e-commerce performance through various applications and technologies.

This opens up opportunities for us to creatively explore ways in which AI can be integrated into e-commerce business models and utilized to save time or money by increasing efficiency.

In the following chapters, specific ways in which the introduction of AI can improve the operations of electronic commerce will be explained with the help of expert and professional literature. This paper will attempt to answer research questions about the models of AI application in e-commerce.

Also, this paper uses a descriptive before/after comparison across three major e-commerce platforms (WooCommerce, Shopify, Magento). For each platform, baseline workflows are briefly described, followed by newly introduced AI-based features (e.g., product content generators, AI chat assistants, automated store setup). This structured comparison serves as the methodological basis of the paper and addresses how AI concretely changes platform capabilities.

2. AI AND ITS IMPORTANCE

AI systems generally operate by processing large volumes of labeled training data, identifying patterns and correlations within the data, and using these patterns to predict future outcomes. For instance, a chatbot trained with numerous text conversation examples can learn to produce realistic interactions with users, while an image recognition system can learn to identify and describe objects in pictures by examining millions of samples (Nimbalkar & Berad, 2021).

From the perspective of business system owners and stakeholders, when investing, it is necessary to ask one or both of two questions: Does the investment save money (or time) or Does the investment make money?

AI does both – the rare combination of making money and saving money means it's essential to add to your business. Therefore, if there are such positive impacts, the answer to the question of whether it is worth investing or ultimately exploring the impact and planning the implementation of AI in e-commerce businesses is clear.

We've reached a point where everyone is talking about artificial intelligence, and many are using it. If business owners don't also consider the possibility and advantages of implementing AI in their e-commerce stores, the longer they go without using it, the wider the gap becomes with the competition.

3. AI IN E-COMMERCE BUSINESS

There are many ways to harness the power of AI to improve the overall e-commerce experience. Almost every link in the chain of retail business can find a way to implement AI and thus enhance the entire operation.

AI is not a singular technology; it encompasses various models. There are four leading AI technologies used in e-commerce (Shopify, 2025):

- Natural language processing (NLP): Natural language processing is dedicated to equipping computers with the ability to understand and produce human language
- Machine learning (ML): Machine learning employs statistical methods and algorithms to allow computers to learn from data and make predictions or decisions without explicit programming. Deep learning models, including transformers and large language models (LLMs) like OpenAI's ChatGPT, utilize layered algorithms to enhance data comprehension.
- Computer vision (CV): Computer vision is a field of artificial intelligence that enables computers to interpret information from images and videos.
- Data mining: Data mining is the process of discovering data to inform AI algorithms and systems.

3.1 Personalized product recommendations

Among the primary applications of artificial intelligence in e-commerce, personalized product recommendations for online shoppers lead to increased conversion rates. Utilizing big data, AI in e-commerce influences customer choices based on its knowledge of past purchases, browsing habits, and searched products (Nimbalkar & Berad, 2021).

3.2 Chatbots

The customer service aspect has become integral to the growth of every business. While companies now offer faster transactions, they often lack 24/7 customer support. An artificial intelligence assistant (chatbot) serves as a key solution, employing natural language processing to automatically address consumer inquiries, handle basic voice commands, and offer product recommendations (Gururaj, 2021).

While engaging with customers, some systems have the capability to recognize the sentiment of a user, discerning emotions such as frustration or impatience. It adapts its responses accordingly and can signal or elevate the issue to a human when necessary. Additionally, AI systems also categorize information from interactions, which helps with tasks like sending the customer to the right department.

3.3 Review and Comment Filtering

For prominent brands, manually analyzing every product review or comment would be exceedingly resource-intensive. Natural language processing offers a solution by parsing messages and organizing them based on sentiment, product mentions, or specific phrases. This enables a comprehensive understanding of customer sentiments regarding products, guiding future product development and marketing strategies (SalientProcess, 2024).

Additionally, AI could also respond to these comments, of course, adapting to the emotion and manner in which the user left their review, or simply filter them and leave them for a human to respond to.

3.4 Fraud detection and prevention

The financial and e-commerce industries are increasingly vulnerable to the threat of fraudulent activities. With fraudsters becoming more sophisticated, it's imperative to utilize advanced tools and technologies to effectively combat this menace (Vyas, 2023).

3.5 Dynamic pricing

Even for small-scale online retailers with limited inventory, maintaining continuous and long-term price adjustments poses a substantial challenge. However, artificial intelligence technology, capable of swiftly processing vast amounts of data, has largely addressed the issue of automating pricing for a wide array of products (Song et al., 2019).

Additionally, it's important to consider the possibility of monitoring competitor prices and then, based on the given strategy, train AI to dynamically adjust prices. Of course, this would need to be implemented with great care, regarding the business impact and considering the possibilities of implementation related to a specific industry and the way businesses generate profits.

3.6. Dynamic website content

Machine learning has the capability to integrate dynamic content into website, adapting in response to user behaviors. For instance, it can generate a list of product recommendations. By observing users' browsing patterns and interactions, AI learns and tailors suggestions based on similar characteristics. Additionally, recommendation algorithms can leverage aggregate data from other users, as well as user-provided information like shoe size entered in their profile.

3.7 Targeted Marketing Campaigns

AI functions as a key enabler of automation and data-driven decision making in e-commerce. Artificial intelligence can assist marketers in crafting targeted marketing campaigns, particularly in the realm of ad targeting. Through machine learning capabilities, AI can differentiate between various stages of consumer behavior, such as browsing, actual conversion, and exploratory actions, enabling the retargeting of prospects with a higher likelihood of conversion (Haleem et al., 2022).

3.8 Sales and Demand Forecasting

Artificial Intelligence serves a pivotal and widespread role in sales forecasting by facilitating the analysis of vast amounts of customer data. This enables individuals and experts to gain valuable and accurate insights efficiently. Utilizing Artificial Intelligence is advantageous due to the time and resources saved in comparison to manual analysis, which often consumes days, hours, or even months to complete (Soni, 2020).

Attention should be paid to the ability of Artificial Intelligence to analyze the e-commerce industry and match it with events that can influence increased demand and interest from end customers.

3.9 Automated processing

Artificial intelligence's decision-making capabilities are equally beneficial behind the scenes, assuming control of repetitive administrative duties. In e-commerce, companies commonly employ AI to automate tasks such as managing returns and preventing fraud (SalientProcess, 2024).

In this context, AI, for example, can be trained to handle return requests based on the customer's location. If approved, it can update all necessary system entries and guide the customer on the return process and refund method.

3.10 Managing Abandoned Carts through AI

Users often abandon their purchases when they already have certain products in their cart. There are two main approaches to inventory management when a product is placed in the cart. Business owners can choose to reserve these products while they are in the cart (which can pose a problem that AI can help solve), or to update the stock of that product only after the transaction is completed. In the case of the second approach, with large retail chains and their promotions, conflicts may arise between customers buying same product that are going out of stock, causing dissatisfaction for some.

When reserving product inventory upon adding to the cart, AI can make an effort to send specific notifications with incentives to complete the purchase when it detects an abandoned cart or simply release the inventory after failed attempts.

A comprehensive review stresses that AI applications like chatbots, visual/voice search, recommendation engines or fake review detection consistently enhance personalization and automation across the entire customer journey (Sristava, 2021).

3.11 Before and after AI features across platforms

To illustrate how AI concretely alters e-commerce workflows, for each of the three major platforms—WooCommerce, Shopify, and Magento baseline processes are contrasted with newly introduced AI-driven features that reshape them.

Table 1: Platform specific before/after highlights

Platform	Before AI	After AI (new features, 2023-2025)
WooCommerce	Manual product copy; rule-based customer support	Woo AI Product Assistant generates product titles/descriptions from prompts. AI chat assistants available via plugins (WooCommerce, 2023).
Shopify	Store setup and personalization required extensive manual configuration	I Store Builder generates complete stores from keywords; Tariff Guide supports customs calculations (Reuters, 2025; Shopify, 2025).
Magento	Product content and metadata creation fully manual	Marketplace extensions (e.g., Meetanshi AI Content Generator, MageComp ChatGPT Generator) enable automated product descriptions and SEO metadata (Adobe Commerce Marketplace, n.d.).

4. CONCLUSION

AI is rapidly becoming our reality. It has permeated all aspects of society, and anyone who wants to keep up with the times must investigate the impact of AI on their work. It is necessary to find a way in which the application of AI will be beneficial to us.

The electronic commerce sector requires continuous monitoring of technological trends. This necessity is driven by the very nature of e-commerce as a business that is inherently dependent on technology. Choosing the right platform for electronic commerce can be a challenging task, which could be topic of future work.

Regardless of the platform chosen, a common denominator is the inevitability of integrating AI into e-commerce business processes. Increasing operational efficiency is the top priority, from global economies to small online businesses. This is where AI steps in and shines in its full glory.

Additionally, a high level of attention is mandatory when leveraging AI in e-commerce. It is crucial to consider all factors, such as the nature of the product, the competitive landscape, and consumers.

5. FUTURE WORK

With a multitude of solutions for facilitating and enhancing the development of e-commerce shops, an interesting topic for research is the possibilities of introducing the listed AI applications in collaboration with some of the platforms.

Relying on the online tool and service specialized in providing information about the technologies used for building and managing websites – "BuiltWith.com", we will highlight several globally and locally popular e-commerce platforms that provide complete support for creating an e-commerce store. E-commerce platforms make life easier for business owners who want to start their online journey.

Figure 1: Platform Usage Distribution in the Top 1 Million Sites by Traffic Worldwide (BuiltWith, n.d.)

In the top 1 million sites by traffic, leading positions are occupied by Shopify, WooCommerce, and Magento. A similar situation is observed in the Western Balkans region (data aggregated from "BuiltWith" for countries: Serbia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Croatia, and Montenegro) and Europe, where Shopify and WooCommerce are the leading e-commerce development platforms in most countries.

Shopify is one of the popular B2C e-commerce tools. It was launched in the mid-2000s and became increasingly popular in the 2010s. Shopify constitutes a powerful technological resource that equips individuals with a full suite of business functions, including payment, marketing, shipping, and customer engagement (Dushnitsky & Stroube, 2021).

During the last couple of years, WordPress has outgrown any other Content Management Solution worldwide. Numerous websites are built using WordPress on a daily basis. WordPress is even popular among large companies. Currently, about a quarter of all websites worldwide are powered by WordPress (Ravensbergen, 2015). WooCommerce is a plugin for WordPress that turns the website into a complete online store. For all of that, only a few minutes are needed for initial setup, which leads us to the fact that WooCommerce is also a low-code solution for starting an e-commerce store.

Magento is open source e-commerce platform aimed at web site designers, developers, and business owners who are looking for a complete e-commerce web site solution. Varien, the company responsible for building Magento, has set a new standard for open-source applications. One of the most impressive aspects of Magento is the use of the Zend Framework which allows for the separation of the Model-View-Controller (MVC) which separates its core operations from functionality and appearance. Magento gives the flexibility to completely customize the web site to suit business needs (McCombs & Banh, 2010). For individuals without any coding experience, establishing a website on the Magento platform presents significant challenges. Nevertheless, having coding expertise is advantageous across all e-commerce platforms, enabling users to fully leverage the capabilities of their chosen system. Due to the relatively high technical demands of Magento compared to other platforms, it is predominantly utilized by large enterprises that possess dedicated technical teams.

Below is a summary table of the most important characteristics for e-commerce to compare these three e-commerce platforms, which we have identified as the most popular. The data is summarized from the platform's websites and is up-to-date with the writing date of the paper.

Table 2: Summary of most popular e-commerce platforms

	Shopify	WooCommerce	Magento
Cost	Paid	Free	Free
Products	Unlimited	Unlimited	Unlimited
Hosting	Included	Not Included	Not Included
Payment Gateway	Wide range	Wide range	Wide range
Theme and Design variety	Medium	Large	Large
Customization	Medium	Large	Large
SEO capabilities	Good	Excellent	Excellent

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